

Variables of Sports Competition as Correlate of Physiological and Social Development of Tertiary School Athletes

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Abstract:- This study aims to ascertain the Variables of Sports Competition as Correlates to the Physiological and social Development of Tertiary School Athletes. It is a quantitative research that utilizes a descriptive - corellational method of research. Furthermore, it utilizes sets of questionnaires with 103 student athletes from Marinduque State College who are enrolled in Academic Year 2021- 2022 and Academic year 2022- 2023.

The findings of the study revealed that majority of the athletes are preparing for a regional sport competition in 1 month duration before the competition or also known as their rigid training. Most of the participants disclosed that they have a coach who has an empathetic style that values sportsmanship above all and make decision that consider the athletes' opinion. Furthermore, the participants disclosed that majority of them receives cash incentives if the athlete won a medal (bronze, silver, or gold) in a competition and gain a monthly allowance being a varsity athlete in regards to awards and incentive they receive. Moreover, participants revealed that the institution they belong creates an interventive programs for student – athlete development. Respondents of the study perceived that peer support is the most essential in sports competition related variable. Majority of them exposed that their peers support them and cheer them up when they feel down in their performance in a competition and shows their intention as proud team mates and peers. Lastly, the salient findings of the study revealed that the correlation of sports related variables and physiological development of athletes are significantly related to each other. Likewise, as to social development of athletes, the result of the study disclosed that the correlation of Sports related variables and social development of athletes are significantly related to each other as well.

Keywords:- Sports Competition Related Variables, Physiological Development of Athletes, Social Development of Athletes.

I. INTRODUCTION

Everyone has their own way of expressing their selves to different people, some of them used to exposed their skills and talents to public, few of them prefer to hide their capabilities. Some of us use to prove their selves that they can make a difference, contribute and give part to the society through such skills we display and some use to compete with their selves to develop such capabilities they strived for. This manner can be seen to some athletes who are striving hard to gain success and contribute to society through sports. As we all know, sports are recognized by many people in our society

or even the world. Sport refers to any competitive physical activity or game that seeks to develop, preserve, or enhance physical ability and skills while also offering fun to participants and, in some cases, spectators. Via casual or organized participation in sports, one can enhance one's physical health. Hundreds of sports exist, ranging from single-player competitions to multi-player events. Sport is widely accepted as a system of activities based on physical athleticism or dexterity, with major competitions such as the Olympic Games admitting only sports that meet this definition.

Sport is a broad term that encompasses a variety of organized activities that differ in their culture, physicality, structure (ranging from community recreational programs to school programs to elite sport programs at the university and professional levels), availability and quality of coaching, and the intensity with which winning is valued over participation. Recognizing sport's diversity, the sport community has shown an increasing interest in structuring sport to provide a quality experience for youth that has a positive impact on broad health and social outcomes. Then Long-Term Athlete Development Model (LTAD; Balyi, Way, & Higgs, 2013) for example, identifies several core components that should be targeted in youth sport including: (1) skill development, appropriate to the developmental stage (maturation) of the athlete; (2) presence of supportive, encouraging, and trained adult coaches; and (3) a focus on both sport-specific skill development and individual development related to acquisition of transferrable life skills (e.g. time management), and the regulation of behaviour and emotion. Coaches play an important role in youths' sport experiences, according to both the LTAD model and research on sport and youth development (Balyi et al., 2013; Hogue, Fry, Fry, & Pressman, 2013; MacDonald, Côté, Eys, & Deakin, 2011). As a result, the relationship between sport participation and psychological and social outcomes may be influenced by the quality of the sport experience, which is heavily influenced by coaches.

Recent research has shown that the presence of a competitor can increase physical effort over both short and long durations. Competitiveness has also been shown to increase physical motivation, such as motivation to practice a sport. A better understanding of how competition improves performance may help shed light on how to improve cognitive performance (e.g., memory in the classroom). For example, if the presence of a competitor affected attention, we may expect to see an effect at encoding, since attention is one of many necessary components for accurate encoding. However, if the presence of a competitor is affecting memory

retention, we may expect a difference regarding long-term memory, but not short-term memory. Furthermore, competition could affect components of memory without affecting attention at all. (DiMenichi, Bryan 2015)

Sports physiology studies how exercise affects the body's structure and function. An expert in sports physiology uses specialized tests and equipment to evaluate an athlete's performance. This offers helpful information that coaches, fitness trainers, health educators, sports trainers, and exercise physiologists may utilize to support their players in performing at their best. By understanding how the body works during exercise and applying scientific principles, exercise and sport physiology aims to improve performance by enabling your body to train more effectively, perform better, and recover faster. Exercise intensity, duration, frequency, and environmental factors all affect how the body reacts to it physiologically. (Bertaggia, et al. 2019)

Peers can also play an important role throughout athlete development. During the sampling years, peers are one of the main reasons why children participate in organized and unorganized sports, as well as remain involved and motivated to practice sports later in their development. As the athlete progresses in sport (up to the investment years), friends outside of sport are considered an important source of support since they tend to fulfill athletes' motivational and emotional needs (Côté et al., 2007; Fraser-Thomas et al., 2008a,b; Barreiros et al., 2013; Bruner et al., 2013, Mesquita et al, 2021).

Many of the social skills youngsters will need throughout their lives can be developed through team sports. They learn to work together, to be less egotistical, and to pay attention to other people. Additionally, it fosters a sense of community in youth. They gain new acquaintances and expand their social connections outside of school. Accepting discipline is a crucial component of team play. Students who participate in sports are expected to adhere to the rules, respect judges' judgments, and comprehend that misbehavior may result in consequences. It teaches them to obey the coach, officials, and other adults. They learn about teamwork through sport as well.

Generally speaking, participation in sports has a significant overall impact on students. Along with being physically active, they also have considerably stronger

This study focuses on the Sports Competition related Variables that corellates with the Physiological and Social Development of Athletes. This study was conducted at Marinduque State College. Participant of the study were Athletes who are bonafied students in the said institution that participated in regional sports competition (STRASUC). Some participants who joined on STRASUC and also participated on a national sports competition (PASUC) are also part of this study. Students who also compete in Regional or even higher level of sports competition during their elementary and highschool, were also part of this study. It presents a systematic review about athletes' Physiological and social development in participating a sports competition. This study delimits athlete's who are already graduated in the said institution. This study will not cover other matter such as

emotional fortitude and better mental acuity. Numerous studies have looked into these advantages, and academics from all over the world concur that athletics should play an important role in higher education. Participation in sports give students the chance to experience the strength of a common objective or target, especially when they play in teams. Simply put, the ideal setting for honing the great traits of teamwork is a competitive sport one. Sports promote inclusivity when properly supervised and facilitated, and for international students, this is an additional chance to be able to connect with one another. Students can have a second support system—a family away from home—by joining a team.

Self-esteem is a delicate topic with many variables to take into account. In fact, it's important to keep in mind that competitive sports feature a winner and a loser on opposite sides of the coin. While winning in athletics may enhance a player's confidence, losing can have a significant impact on a student's performance after a competition. The responsibility ultimately rests with the institutions and its workers, who must be prepared and highly skilled to deal with such circumstances. If used properly, sports may help children appreciate the virtues of competition—being gracious in loss and humble in triumph. Leaders are created in both scenarios.

A. Objective of the study

It is clear that joining a sport competition may give you benefits in physiological and social aspects. Developing your physical attributes and social skills are essential in participating sports competition considering that there are diverse athletes and coaches that you will encounter. Strategy and Decision making will also improve in participating a sports competition and it can be used not only in sport but in real life situation. Therefore, the aim of this study is to identify Variables of Sports Competition that correlates with the physiological and social features of the athletes. The researcher sought to find a solution regarding development of athletes in physiological and social aspects. The study also aims to ascertain facts about how the athletes perceived sports competition related variables. This study will reveal evidences that Sports competition related variables affects the physiological and social development of athletes.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

academic performances and other extra- curricular activities of the student- athletes that is not related on sports competition.

This study intends to to know the Variables of Sports Competition as correlates of the physiological and Social Development of Tertiary School Athletes. The finding of this study could be very significant to the University or School, for physical education instructors, Coach or mentor and also for the student – athletes as they provide empirical data for Physiological and Social Development of Athletes. Likewise for future researchers who wish to conduct a study related to sports competition and Holistic development of an Athlete.

- To the University or School, the result of this study may help the performance of the institution in joining a Sports Competition and this serves as basis for the selection of athletes since the result reveal some interventions that can be adapt by the school.
- To Physical Education Instructors, this may serve as guide to broaden the understanding about sports competition related variables that corellates with the physiological and social development of athletes. It can be applied in the pedagogy and make as an example to our students in discussing related topics.
- To the Coaches and Trainors, this may serve as guide in recognizing factors that affect the physiological and social development of athletes in sports competition. It may also help us coaches and trainors to consider some issues that athletes are afraid to tell us in regards to coaching style that affects their performance in the competition.
- To the Student – Athletes, this study may increase the level of understanding on your physiological and social development that sports competition provide you as an athlete. This may also be a guide for athletes to understand some characteristics of your peers or team mates and other traits than you can apply in the coompetition.
- To the future reasearchers, this may serve as your reference in writing your study about sports competition and development of athletes since this study caters information particularly in physiological and social aspects of athletes. It may provide readers basic knowledge about Sports Competition and may gain insights in the holistic development of athletes.

This study is a quantitative research that utilizes a descriptive - corellational method of research. It discusses the relationship between variables of sports competition to physiological and social development of tertiary school Athlete. This method will also examine the relationship and differences between the variables studied. This study was conducted at Marinduque State College where the institution is part of the so-called Southern Tagalog Regional Association of States, Universities and Colleges (STRASUC) which participated in the STRASUC Olympics. The respondents of this study are the student – athlete of Marinduque State College enrolled in Academic year 2021 – 2022, and academic year 2022 – 2023 who compete in regional or even higher level of involvement in sports ceompetition. The participants of the study were chosen because they have more experience and gain some information that this study needs in terms of variables that correlates with their Physiological and social development of an athlete.

The data gathered from 103 student - athletes of Marinduque State College using Purposive Sampling method. Student – athletes of the aforementioned institution were chosen for this study since they have the characteristics required in obtaining the goals of the study. This research study utilized a researcher made questionnaire to gather relevant data that would answer the problems of the study. The instrument used in the study is categorize in to two parts.

Part I contains the Profile of the participants, and part II deals with items relating to variables in sports competition that corresponds to the physiological and social development of athletes.

The research instrument undergone validation evaluation and assessed by instructors from Marinduque State College who has the expretise in relates to the research. The researcher reviewed and improved the instrument according to the suggestions of the validators.

In order to have a thorough study about Variables of Sports Competition that Corellates to the physiological and Social development of tertiary school athletes, consultation to the adviser took place. The researcher presented the concept formulated and prepared to the panel members and some recommendations and suggestions were discussed to further imprve the content of the study. The study was conducted in-person sessions since Marinduque State College implements face to face classes. A request letter is made in conducting the study. The participants of the study were given sets of questionnaires and guided in answering by means if discussing the instructions stated in the questionnaires. The Respondents were given enough time to answer the questionnaires. The researcher received information from the completed questionnaires of the respondents. Before giving the data to the statistician, the researcher documented the information. The data underwent statistical processing.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the results, the analysis and interpretation of data gathered from the answers to the questionnaires distributed to the field. The said data were presented in tabular form in accordance with the specific question sited on the statement of the problem.

A. Profile of the Respondents

Respondents of the study were student – athletes of Marinduque State College enrolled in Academic year 2021 – 2022, and academic year 2022 – 2023 who compete in regional or even higher level of involvement in sports ceompetition. Respondents were ask as to their Age, gender, number of years, as an athlete, Sports specialization, level of sports competition involvement, and family's monthly income.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Age

Age	Frequency	Percent
18 – 20 years	55	53.4
21 – 23 years	40	38.8
24 – 26 years	8	7.8
Total	103	100%

According to this table, 53.4% of the respondent has the age of 18- 20 years old, 38.8% has the age of 21 – 23 years, and 7.8% are from 24 – 26 years old. Therefore most of the

respondents who answered the questionnaire came from 18 – 20 years of age.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Male	69	67.0
Female	34	33.0
Total	103	100%

Based on the table, Male participants are 69 getting 67% while female participants are 34 with a 33% total of

respondents. Therefore the majority of the participants are male since it has a 67% of the population.

Table 3: Distribution of Respondents to the no. of years as athlete in their sport

Years Playing	Frequency	Percent
1 – 3 years	19	18.4
4 – 6 years	24	23.3
7 – 9 years	40	38.8
10 – 12 years	19	18.4
13 – 15 years	1	1.0
Total	103	100%

This table shows how long or how many years the respondents’ playing their specialized sport. It can be gleaned from the data that there are nineteen (19) respondents who played 1 – 3 years of their sport garnering 18.4% of the respondents response. 24 of the respondents answered they were playing their sports 4 – 6 years gaining 23.3% of the respondents’ response. Moreover, 40 of the respondents were playing their sport around 7 – 9 years, turn’s- out 38.8 of the

respondents were in these years playing specialized sport, while 19 of the participants’ response 10 – 12 years of playing their specialized sport with a 18.4 % of the response of the respondents. Lastly, 1 of the participants belong to 13 – 15 years of playing specialized sport getting a 1.0% to the respondents responses. Therefore, majority of the respondents were playing 7- 9 years as for their specialized sport event.

Table 4: Distribution of Respondents as to their Specialized Sports

Sport	Frequency	Percent
Arnis	7	6.8
Athletics	16	15.5
Badminton	7	6.8
Baseball	12	11.7
Basketball	13	12.6
Billiards	4	3.9
Chess	1	1.0
Dance Sports	3	2.9
Lawn Tennis	7	6.8
Sepak Takraw	5	4.9
Softball	5	4.9
Table Tennis	7	6.8
Volleyball	16	15.5
Total	103	100%

This table shows the specialized sports that the participants playing for the sport competition. With a total of 103 Participants, 7 are playing arnis as their specialized sport with a percentage of 6.8% of the respondents. 16 participants specialized with Athletics got 15.5% and has the highest total of participants. Furthermore, 7 participants (6.8%) has the expertise when it comes to Badminton, while 12 student – athletes (11.7%) form the participants choose Baseball as their primary sport. Moreover, participants who played Basketball as their sport were 13 getting 12.6% of the respondents data, 4 of the participants (3.9%) are experts in billiards, and 1 participant is playing Chess as it gain 1.0% of

the respondents’ data. 3 of the respondent are experts in Dance Sports with a 2.9% gathered in the respondents data, 7 of the participants (6.8%) were playing Lawn Tennis, 5 of the participants (4.9%) were playing Sepak Takraw as their sport, same with softball 5 participants are in this data gathering a 4.9% percentage, then 7 participants were playing table tennis as their sport with a 6.8% of the data, and lastly, 16 participants (15.5%) of this study were playing Volleyball as their specialized sport. Therefore, the sports which played by the participants most are Athletics and Volleyball getting 16 participants, and the least sport to be played in this study is Chess with only 1 participant.

Table 5: Distribution of Respondents as to Level of Sports Competition Participations

Level of Sports Competition	Frequency	Percent
Regional	90	87.4
National	11	10.7
International	2	1.9
Total	103	100.0

This table tackles the participants’ level of sports competition they joined. According to the table, there are 90 participants of this study (87.4%) who played and compete at the regional competition, followed by 11 participants (10.7%) were participated in a National Competition, and lastly, 2 of

the participants (1.9%) were engaged in an International Sports Competition. Accordingly, the most participated sports competition of the respondents is the Regional Competition and the least sports competition is the International sports competition.

Table 6: Distribution of Respondents’ Family Monthly Income

Family’s Monthly Income	Frequency	Percent
Below ₱10, 000	31	30.1
₱11, 000 - ₱13, 000	21	20.4
₱13, 001 - ₱15, 000	20	19.4
₱15, 001 - ₱17, 000	13	12.6
₱17, 000 above	18	17.5
Total	103	100.0

This table shows the respondents’ family monthly income, this is part of the profiling of the participants since sports equipment of the family will somewhat depends on the financial availability of the family of the athlete. Of the respondents, 31 (30.1%) had the monthly income of below ₱10, 000, 21 (20.4%) were having an income of ₱11, 000 – ₱13, 000 monthly. While 20 (19.4%) of the participants revealed that their monthly income is about ₱13, 001 – ₱15, 000, 13 of the participants (12.6%) were getting monthly income range from ₱15, 000 – ₱17, 000, and lastly, 18

(17.5%) of the participants earned ₱17, 000 above monthly. Thus, the most response in family’s monthly income is Below ₱10, 000 and the least response is ₱17, 000 above.

B. Related Variables

Student – athlete or the respondents of the study were assessed in what they received or experienced in joining a sports competition, these related variables include Training Methodology, Coaching Style, Awards and Incentives, Administrative support and lastly, peer support.

Table 7: Perception of the Respondents towards Sports Competition Related Variables as to Training Methodology

TRAINING METHODOLOGY	Mean	Std. Deviation	interpretation	Description
One month Training Preparation on a sport Competition	4.47	.76	Agree	Effective
Undergo Series of training and workshops to other Sports Organization 3 months before competition	4.18	.75	Agree	Effective
Continuous Self Training even without competition to Participate.	4.28	.74	Agree	Effective
6 months Training preparation to concentrate in sports competition	4.04	.88	Agree	Effective
Training is designed for 1 year preparation includes local competition before entering higher level of competition	4.18	.84	Agree	Effective
Training includes body conditioning	4.37	.71	Agree	Effective
Training includes longer intervals of physical exercises without breaks or rest periods.	4.05	.89	Agree	Effective
Training is intended to a planned set of exercises that can gradually help expand the range of motions.	4.26	.79	Agree	Effective
Training includes exercises in which the body exerts force in short interval	4.19	.75	Agree	Effective
Training alternates between short bursts of high-intensity workout and periods of rest and recovery.	4.41	.89	Agree	Effective
Overall	4.24	0.80	Agree	Effective

Table reveals that the respondents perceived training methodology as effective indicator and all agreed with the overall mean of 4.24 with a Standard Deviation of 0.80. According to the data presented, the highest mean is the Training preparation for at least 1 month before joining a sport competition with a mean of 4.47. According to D. Zahradnik (2012) before entering an athlete to a competition, it must first undergo with the “pre-competition phase” that

includes 2 – 4 weeks of preparation and it should not be very long because it may result in decrease in motivation or problems with maintained reached fitness level without top competitions etc., which corroborate with the highest mean in this table. Nonetheless, the least mean in this table is the 6 months preparation before joining a competition with a mean of 4.04, which contradict the “pre – competition phase” but still effective and agreed by the respondents.

Table 8: Perception of the Respondents towards Sports Competition Related Variables as to Coaching Style

Perception of the Respondents Towards Sports Competition Related Variables as to Coaching Style

Coaching Style	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation	Description
Coach has an empathetic style that values sportsmanship above all and make decisions that consider the athletes' side.	4.48	.68	Agree	Effective
Coach is a demanding one, focus on situational approach not on consistent practice	3.71	1.15	Agree	Effective
Let his athletes explore more on their sport and decide by their own. Expect that athlete is accountable on their own training.	4.00	.99	Agree	Effective
Embraces the whole person, recognizing that every athlete is a human first and a player second, and prioritizes growth accordingly	4.26	.79	Agree	Effective
Coach who can create a far- reaching, positive influence on the lives of his athletes	4.40	.74	Agree	Effective
Coach is present and guide his athletes during training	4.31	.79	Agree	Effective
Disciplined his athletes by giving punishments in every mistake during training	4.05	.87	Agree	Effective
Coach gives athletes' rewards and condition to motivate his players to perform well.	4.30	.80	Agree	Effective
Coach attends the training once a week to check the athletes progress	4.07	1.07	Agree	Effective
Gives all the instruction to athletes and let them do the task by their own.	4.28	.96	Agree	Effective
Overall	4.19	0.89	Agree	Effective

This table affirms that the respondents perceived coaching style as effective and all agreed with the overall mean of 4.19 with a standard deviation of 0.89. The data shows that the highest mean and agreed most is the coach has an empathetic style that values sportsmanship above all and make decisions that consider the athletes' side, with a mean of 4.48. According to B. Knight (2018), best coaching style for athlete is the Democratic coaching wherein it can facilitate a healthy team culture in which the coach and players makes decision together. Though the coach ultimately has the final say, the athletes also have a responsibility to find a way that works best for them, which support the utmost response in the data. Inversely, the least mean agreed by the respondents is

the coach is a demanding one, focus on situational approach and not on consistent practice, with a mean of 3.71. “Autocratic coaches assume responsibility for every decision, little room is left for team input or innovation. Coaches must be confident that their way is always right, risking a reputation as a dictator that can compromise team camaraderie and goodwill.” -P. Summit, (2018). This disproves the fact that coaches and athletes must have a harmonious relationship to promote a balance connection. In addition, coaches from Marinduque State College emphasizes balance connection and affect athletes' entire lives for the better progress.

Table 9: Perception of the Respondents towards Sports Competition Related Variables as to Awards and Incentives

Awards and Incentives	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation	Description
Athletes Receives Cash Incentives if they won bronze, silver, or gold medal and a monthly allowance being a varsity athlete.	4.49	.73	Agree	Effective
Have free medical and dental consultation in government hospitals or clinic.	3.96	.93	Agree	Effective
Have full access for different sports training seminars and workshop	4.00	.93	Agree	Effective
Athletes receive recognition given by the institution and awarded as Athlete of the year.	4.24	.85	Agree	Effective
Recognized by government officials as one of the prodigies of the province in sport.	4.22	.86	Agree	Effective
Overall	4.18	0.86	Agree	Effective

This table conveys the respondents’ awards and incentives they received or experience in joining a sports competition. Respondents perceived and agreed that awards and incentives is also effective as related variable in sports competition, with the overall mean of 4.18 with standard deviation of 0.87. The data shows that the highest mean and most agreed by the respondents that student -athletes receives Cash incentives if they won bronze, silver, or gold medal, and a monthly allowance being a varsity athlete. According to the Republic Act 10699 known as the “National Athletes and Coaches Benefits and Incentives Act” was enacted into law, expanding the benefits received under RA 9064 (Approved on April 5, 2001). The declared policy of RA 10699 is to “promote excellence in sports by looking after the welfare of national athletes and coaches competing for the country and by providing benefits and incentives for national athletes and other athletes who win in international sports competition and

bring honor and recognition to the country”, which relates with the athlete receiving cash and incentives from the government and institutions even in a regional sport competition.

However, the least agreed in the indicator by the respondents is student – athletes have a free medical and dental consultation in government hospitals or clinic. In the Republic Act No. 10699 also known as “Sports Benefits and Incentives Act of 2001” under Section IV states that Athletes and Coaches has a privilege of free medical and dental consultations in government hospitals and similar establishments anywhere in the country. In somewhat related, regional athletes received free medical and dental consultation inside the institution but not on private clinic and government hospitals.

Table 10: Perception of the Respondents towards Sports Competition Related Variables as to Administrative Support

ADMINISTRATIVE SUPPORT	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation	Description
Athletes receive a full Varsity – Scholarship and free Dormitory access of the institution.	3.75	1.13	Agree	Effective
Athletes have full access to the sport facilities and equipment of the institution	3.39	1.18	Moderately Agree	Effective Enough
Athletes receive financial assistance or monthly allowance given by the institution as labor of the athletes’ service.	3.79	.96	Agree	Effective
Institution endorses the athlete from other sectors and sponsorships	3.81	.82	Agree	Effective
The institution creates interventive programs for Student – athletes.	4.20	.90	Agree	Effective
Overall	3.79	1.00	Agree	Effective

Table presents the respondents’ administrative support they get from the institution. Respondents perceived and agreed that administrative support as related variable is Effective since it has an overall mean of 3.79 with a standard deviation of 1.00. Majority of the respondents revealed and most agreed that the institution creates an interventive program for student – athletes with a mean of 4.20. Interventive program includes clubs and league competitions inside the institution. Transitioning to sustainable lifetime physical activity following the end of a competitive sport career can feel daunting after years of focused training for a single sport. As student athletes (SAs) enter this transition,

learning to integrate physical activity within new life commitments can be frustrating when compared to the priority placed on training during college (Smith et al., 2020). These interventions help the student – athlete to gain more skills and experiences and expose with a sport – active environment. Moreover, the least response and moderately agreed or neutral indicator by was the Athletes have full access to the sport facilities and equipment of the institution, with a mean of 3.39. Although facilities and equipment are present in the institution, the availability of these is uncertain since facilities are used also for different events or program of the institution.

Table 11: Perception of the Respondents towards Sports Competition Related Variables as to Peer Support

PEER SUPPORT	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation	Description
Friends/ peer/ Team gives encouragement to compete sports Competition	4.49	.73	Agree	Effective
Watches game and pray for the best of the athletes performance in a competition	4.59	.58	Strongly Agree	Very Effective
Peers displays loyalty and closed bond together as a team	4.45	.72	Agree	Effective
Team assists and help other athletes in training and guiding the team to conquer their weaknesses	4.54	.63	Strongly Agree	Very Effective
Encourage the athletes when feeling down with their performance in a sport competition and show their pure intention as a proud team mate.	4.69	.59	Strongly Agree	Very Effective
Overall	4.55	0.65	Strongly Agree	Very Effective

The table shows the support of the respondents’ they acquire from their peer. Respondents perceived and strongly agreed that peer support is a very effective variable in sport competition with an overall mean of 4.55 with a standard deviation of 0.66. Majority of the respondents revealed and strongly agreed that motivation and encouragement from your peers can boost your confidence in a sport competition giving a positive performance in a game. Not all youth athletes are born with intrinsic motivation to satisfy the rationale for sport participation. The role of peers revolves around friendship, cooperation, and the reinforcement of rules/values among the peer group (Tome, et al., 2012). Peer connection influences motivation through competitive behaviors, collaborative behaviors, evaluative communications, and through their social relationships (Keegan, et al., 2010). This disclosed that peer support can create a positive environment and performance in terms of team play.

Furthermore, Peers that displays loyalty and closed bond together as a team can also be an effective indicator for an athlete, with a mean of 4.45 gets the least yet agreed by the respondent’s data, that this can improve team performance. While it may seem understandable that an athlete becomes attached to teammates and being part of a team, it is clear that sports spectators (those regulars sitting in the stands) can also become so passionate about their team that it becomes part of their identity and affects their well-being. (Wang, S. 2016). This proves that teams with trust, loyalty, and close bonds were better inside and outside the competition.

C. Physiological Development

Respondents of this study was assessed in terms of their Physiological development, it includes Upper body strength and endurance, lower body strength and endurance, flexibility, cardio – vascular fitness, injuries and physical stress, Experience, Activity level, diet, obstruction to hypokinetic diseases, and personal lifestyle.

Table12: Respondents’ Perception on their Physiological Development

Physiological Dev.	Mean Range	Std. Deviation	Interpretation	Performance Level
Upper body strength and Endurance	4.16	0.89	Agree	Very Satisfactory
Lower body Strength and endurance	4.04	0.97	Agree	Very Satisfactory
Flexibility	3.83	1.14	Agree	Very Satisfactory
Cardio- vascular fitness	4.08	0.93	Agree	Very Satisfactory
Injuries and Physical Stress	3.83	1.14	Agree	Very Satisfactory
Experience	3.83	1.14	Agree	Very Satisfactory
Activity Level	4.16	0.89	Agree	Very Satisfactory
Diet	3.99	1.02	Agree	Very Satisfactory
Obstruction of Hypokinetic Diseases	3.51	1.03	Agree	Very Satisfactory
Personal Life Style	4.30	0.94	Agree	Very Satisfactory
Overall	3.97	.22	Agree	Very Satisfactory

The table shows the Respondents’ indicators under the Physiological development. With an overall mean of 3.97, it shows that the Performance level of the respondents in terms of Physiological development is Very Satisfactory. Respondents perceived and agreed that personal lifestyle fits most in physiological development of athletes, with the highest overall mean of 4.30 with a standard deviation of 0.94

and recognized as a positive variable. Majority of the respondents revealed that they eat breakfast before engaging in vigorous training or exercise. However, some of the respondents are taking a quick bath after workout or training. According to (Metrifit, 2022) An athlete’s lifestyle is the foundation of their well-being and potential. It is the set of habits and attitudes that form the pattern of how they go about

their daily lives. Understanding optimal performance requires self-awareness about how lifestyle affects your readiness to train, compete and win! A balanced healthy lifestyle is crucial for success. To discount it as unimportant and not an essential part of athletic preparation is the downfall of many an athlete that had the potential for greatness. This supports that Personal Lifestyle affects Physiological Development of an athlete.

Nonetheless, Obstruction of Hypokinetic Diseases takes the least agreed but still a positive indicator under physiological development of Athletes, with an overall mean of 3.51. Majority of the Respondents affirms that they do regular exercises to avoid such diseases like obesity and hypertension, while some of the respondents admit that they have a family member who acquires such hypokinetic diseases. People who do regular physical activity can reduce their risk of death, regardless of the cause. Active people increase their life expectancy by two years compared to those who are inactive. Sedentary people experience a twenty percent (20%) to two-fold increase in early death compared to active people. Haskell (1995), that increasing physical activity among the adult population would do wonders for the health of the nation because there are so many sedentary

people who could benefit from active lifestyles. He notes that physical inactivity, in combination with poor eating patterns, ranked with alcohol and tobacco use as among the leading preventable contributors to death for adults. If adults who lead sedentary lives would adopt to a more active lifestyle, there would be enormous benefit to public's health and to individual well-being. (Retrieved by B. Ohuruogu, 2016) Some people with a family history of disease may conclude that there is nothing they can do because their heredity works against them. There is no doubt that heredity significantly affects risk of early death from hypokinetic diseases. Studies have suggested that active people are less likely to die early than inactive people with similar genes. This suggests that long-term adherence to physical activity can overcome other risk factors such as heredity- at least for some people. (Dr. B. Ohuruogu, 2016) This proves that obstruction to hypokinetic can affects athletes' physiological development.

D. Social Development

Respondents of this study were assessed in regards to Social Development, it caters motivation, excitement, social support, sportsmanship, communication, reputation, accountability, camaraderie, connection, and Social Roles.

Table13: Respondents' Perception on their Social Development

Social Development	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation	Performance Level
Motivation	4.40	0.62	Agree	Very Satisfactory
Excitement	4.37	0.57	Agree	Very Satisfactory
Social Support	4.31	0.68	Agree	Very Satisfactory
Sportsmanship	4.42	0.65	Agree	Very Satisfactory
Communication	4.57	0.48	Strongly Agree	Excellent
Reputation	4.48	0.62	Agree	Very Satisfactory
Accountability	4.52	0.57	Strongly Agree	Excellent
Camaraderie	4.53	0.58	Strongly Agree	Excellent
Connection	4.41	0.68	Agree	Very Satisfactory
Social Roles	4.59	0.55	Strongly Agree	Excellent
Overall	4.46	0.09	Agree	Very Satisfactory

Table 14 shows the indicator under the social development of an athlete with the overall mean of 4.46 revealing that the performance level of Social Development is Very Satisfactory. Respondents perceived and strongly agreed that social roles has the highest impact in terms of social development of athlete. With an overall- mean of 4.59 with a standard deviation of 0.55, social roles identified as very positive indicator according to the respondents. Majority of the respondents anticipated that they are willing to share their knowledge and skills to train young athletes to improve their performance and character in sports. However, some of the participants displayed and agreed that social support comes at least positive indicator. Social responsibility or social roles concerns individuals when it is exercised by a single person, while it becomes collective when it pertains to groups of people such as companies or sports teams. The popularity that athletes enjoy due to their status as public figures gives them the opportunity to influence the behavior

of many of their fans through public announcements and various forms of promotional activities.

Furthermore, in contrary with the social support for athletes, recent research has also investigated the link between social support and symptoms of depression. Sullivan et al. (Citation 2020) examined the relationships between social support and depressive symptoms in 238 NCAA Division I collegiate athletes. Their results showed weak, negative relationships between all types of social support and depression, as levels of social support decreased the frequency of reported depressive symptoms increased.

E. Significant Relationship between Variables:

The result revealed that most of the Sports related Variables and Physiological Development of athletes are significantly related to each other, using 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance. However, it is likewise revealed that there are some sports related variables which were found not related to Physiological Development of athletes. All indicators under physiological development of athletes was correlated to the training methodology using a 0.05 level of significance. As to coaching style using a 0.05 level of significance, all indicators under physiological development is correlated to coaching style, except Cardio vascular fitness. On the other hand, using a 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance, indicators under physiological development are correlated to Awards and Incentives, excluding cardiovascular fitness as well. Furthermore, as to administrative support using a 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance, it shows that administrative support is correlated with the indicators under physiological development except Cardiovascular fitness. Lastly using a 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance, indicators under the physiological development are all correlated to peer support.

Furthermore, the result revealed that most of the Sports related variables and Social development of athletes are significantly related to each other, using a 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance. However, it is likewise revealed that there are some sports related variables which were found not related to Social Development of athletes. All indicators under social development are correlated with the Training methodology using 0.05 level of significance. As to Coaching style it is correlated with all the indicators of social development using a 0.05 level of significance. Likewise, awards and incentives is correlated with all the indicators of social development of athletes using 0.01 and 0.05 level of significance. As to Administrative support, some of the indicators under social development are correlated to administrative support. However, it is revealed that there are indicators that are not correlated to administrative support under social development such as Excitement, Sportsmanship, Communication, and Accountability. Lastly, as to peer support, all indicators of social development are correlated with peer support using a 0.05 level of significance. Generally, Sports related variables and social development is significantly related to each other.

IV. DISCUSSIONS

The pertinent findings of the study on the profile of the respondents as to age, revealed that majority of the respondents ages, ranges from 18 – 20 years old and most of them are male participants represents 67% of the population. Moreover, majority of the respondents were playing 7 – 9 years. Mostly, respondents were playing Athletics which falls under individual sport event and volleyball which is a team sport. As to their level of sports competition involvement, the uttermost were participated in a regional sports competition. Finally, participants' monthly income is below ₱10, 000.

The salient findings on how the respondents perceived the sports related variables in terms of training methodology, revealed that majority of them are preparing at least 1 month before the competition. As to Coaching style, respondents

revealed that most of them are have a coach who has an empathetic style that values sportsmanship above all and make decision that consider the athletes' opinion. Moreover, respondents receive cash incentives if the athlete won in a competition and have a monthly allowance being a varsity athlete. The institution creates an interventive programs for student – athletes and lastly, respondents exposed that their peers support them and cheer them up when they feel down in their performance in a competition and shows their intention as proud team mates and peers.

The admissible findings on the perception of the respondents to physiological development, majority of the respondents revealed that they can lift things twice as their weight. and can do 20 squats in 3 sets without having fatigue or fainted muscles. Respondents can also bend and flex their arms and legs and can extend to its limit, their breathing is in a regular condition, and fits very well in sports. Most of the respondents' experience fatigue and exhaustion due to long duration of playing. Moreover, respondents played in an amateur and professional sports competition outside the province and applied progressive overload principle in their trainings to definitely easily adjust the level of training. Additionally, majority of the respondents maintain the amount of food they intake during regular training and during competition. Respondents are doing regular exercises to avoid diseases like obesity and hypertension and lastly, majority of the athletes were taking breakfast early in the morning before engaging their selves in training and exercises.

The notable findings on the perception of the respondents to social development of athletes, most of the respondents are determined to accomplish the training to improve their skills and performance in their specialized sport. Majority of them were boost their desire and confidence in playing their sport when they have a professional opponent, their excitement in taking serious matches arises. Furthermore, most of the participants interact with different and diverse athletes who has the same interest as them in sports. They try to make a connection with those athletes that surrounds them. Moreover, respondents use gestures such as thumbs up or applause and hand signals to communicate with their team mates during a game to boost the athletes' confidence and spirit of the game. Athletes displays positive and good character in each match or competition to inspire other athletes with positivity and most of them are appealing with self – assessment to their progress and to their performance and try to be an optimistic individual that they will improve their skill and talents. Respondents disclosed that they understand the strengths and weaknesses of the team mates and recognized the roles of each play and complement one another when they needed it most. In addition, connections of the athletes to other individual who are affiliated in their sport or in management, exposed that making a good impression to other athletes, coaches, and officials of the event is compulsory since in some manner, they will need those connections they have for future references. Lastly, respondents revealed that they are inclined to share their knowledge, skills, and experiences to educate young athletes to refine their performance and character in sports competition.

Finally, the crucial findings on the significant relationship between sports related variables and physiological and social development of athletes were presented in this study. As to physiological Development of athletes, the result of the study revealed that the correlation of sports related variables and physiological development of athletes are significantly related to each other. Likewise, as to social development of athletes, the result of the study disclosed that the correlation of Sports related variables and social development of athletes are significantly related to each other as well.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following is hereby concluded:

- The hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between sports related variables and physiological development of athletes is partially sustained.
- The hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between sports related variables and social development of athletes is not supported by evidence, therefore not accepted.

Based on the above findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are given.

- SUCs may create an interventive programs for student – athletes who participates in a regional and high level of sports competition involvement so that athletes will boost their confidence to upgrade their skills and experiences they gained in the competition.
- SUCs may established Varsity players and engaged them for different opportunities to widen their scopes through sports competition and institutions may offer some benefits for the student – athletes as a reciprocal credit for their hard work and service they lend to the institution. This may also help athletes uplift their motivation to win in a competition.
- Empowering the coaches and Trainers: Exposure to national and International Skills training capability can improve and make the coaches and trainers more adept in meeting the challenges of the times. It will also help them to face new challenges and changes in the field of sports. Inter-institution trainings and benchmarking of best practices are also recommended.
- Athletes Responsibility: Campaigning sports development programs to the community will broaden the understanding of youth in regards to competition and passion in sports. Sense of duty, respect for fellow human beings, morality, and discipline are what create a socially responsible athlete. The popularity that athletes enjoy due to their status as public figures gives them the opportunity to influence the behavior of their supporters through public announcements and various forms of promotional activities. The ethical or ideological theory of athletes' social responsibility assumes that athletes as individuals who are viewed by people as role models, have an obligation to society as a whole to be socially responsible and thus achieve meaningful, positive social change.
- Parallel research may be made to apply the Sports Development and the Personal Development. In future researches, other variables like Motivation, pedagogy, and ethics may be used.

- Future Researchers: Other human aspects such as Psychological, emotional and holistic development of athletes may be created through research referencing. This study may serve as your guide specially in producing systematic and phenomenological studies within the realm of sports community.

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